

Natural Ecosystem and Biodiversity of Bhawal National Park (BNP)

Sourav kanti Bala

Undergraduate Student of Agriculture

IUBAT : International University Of Business Agriculture and Technology
Dhaka, Bangladesh

• Introduction

Protected areas (PAs) are one of the most promising and effective biodiversity conservation strategies and forest resources management sites . Globally, there has been a significant increase of PAs over the last few decades in recognizing importance for the protection of biodiversity. Today, there are more than 100,000 PAs in the world, covering approximately 12% of the world's land surface.

Bangladesh, the world's largest deltaic region, lies in the Northeastern part of South Asia, between 20°34' and 26°38' N latitude and 88°01' and 92°41' E longitude . The majority of the country's land is formed by rivers alluvium adjoining the Ganges and Brahmaputra and their tributaries , which consists of some hilly areas (12%), flood plains (80%) having subtropical monsoon weather . Moreover, Bangladesh is the part of the Indo-Burma biodiversity hotspot, which is one of the 10 globally significant areas with high species biodiversity . For its unique geophysical location, Bangladesh is exceptionally characterized by a rich biological diversity . An estimated 5,700 species of angiosperms of which about 369 species of plants, have been recorded in BNP .

Bhawal National Park (BNP) is one of the historic and rich habitats in Bangladesh. It has a significant influence on environmental, social and economic balance. Bhawal National Park, located in the central region of Bangladesh, is a rich and diverse ecosystem known for its lush deciduous forest. The park covers an area of approximately 5,022 hectares and is home to a variety of flora and fauna. The vegetation primarily consists of Sal (*Shorea robusta*) trees, which dominate the landscape, alongside other species like Gamar (*Gmelina arborea*), Shishu (*Dalbergia sissoo*), and Akashmoni (*Acacia auriculiformis*). This dense forest canopy provides habitat and sustenance for numerous animal species, contributing to the park's vibrant biodiversity.

In addition to its floral diversity, Bhawal National Park supports a wide range of wildlife. The park is inhabited by several species of mammals, including the Indian leopard, Asian black bear, and spotted deer. Birdwatchers can observe a variety of bird species, such as the Asian koel, green bee-eater, and various species of woodpeckers. The park also hosts numerous reptiles and amphibians, enhancing its ecological richness. The combination of diverse plant and animal life makes Bhawal National Park a vital sanctuary for preserving the region's natural heritage.

INDEX

Tropic Name	Page No
Introduction About Bhawal National Park	03 - 05
Natural Ecosystem & Classification	06 - 08
Bhawal National Park ecosystem	09 - 15
Butterfly Research Park of Bhawal National Park	16
Tortoise Enclosed Breeding Centre & Gharial Conservation Centre of BNP	17
Challenges & Overcoming Strategies of Biodiversity of Bhawal National Park	18 - 19
Overview of flora and fauna checklist of Bhawal National Park (BNP)	20
Checklist of Tree Species of Bhawal National Park	22 - 28
Checklist of Shrub Species of Bhawal National Park	29 - 34
Checklist of Herb Species of Bhawal National Park	35 - 40
Checklist of Climber Species of Bhawal National Park	41 - 42
Checklist of Bird Species of Bhawal National Park	44 - 51
Checklist of Amphibian, Mammal & Reptile Species of BNP	51 - 54
Checklist of Butterfly, Insect & Fish Species of BNP	54 - 70
Conclusion	71
References	72 - 73

A Natural Ecosystem and Biodiversity of Bhawal National Park (BNP) .

• Background :

The people of the capital Dhaka and its surrounding areas are interested in recreation and entertainment, in order to preserve the natural forest resources of the region, the establishment of Bhawal National Park was undertaken in 1974-1975 under the sole interest and guidance of Father of the Nation Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujibur Rahman. Later in 1982 Bhawal National Park was established by Gazette Notification No-OO/For 66/81/318 dated 11/05/1982. The main purpose of establishing this park was to create minimum entertainment opportunities for travelers. Development of natural forest resources of Bhawal, preservation of ecological balance through valuable and beautifying planting and conservation of various species, preservation of biodiversity and implementation of scientific research activities. About one million tourists visit this national park every year.

• Location :

Bhawal National Park is located in the natural environment of Gazipur district along the Dhaka-Mymensingh highway, approximately 30 km north of Shahjalal International Airport. As per the master plan, Bhawal National Park has been formed with about 5,022 hectares of forest area, but various developmental activities are mainly limited to 940 hectares of core area. The park is located between 23055' to 24000' north latitude and 90020' to 90025' east longitude. Bhawal National Park is located in Gazipur district headquarters and Sreepur upazila. It is about 13 km from Gazipur district headquarters. Located in North West. A total of 35 mauzas and 136 villages comprise the Bhawal forest area (including buffer zone and core zone). Dhaka-Mymensingh Road on the west side of the park, Rajendrapur Cantonment on the east, Gazipur Sadar on the south and Kapasia Road on the north.

Bhawal National Park Map

• Brief Forest Introduction:

Natural Forests of Bhawal National Park are included in the "Tropical Moist Deciduous Forests". Sal (*Shorea robusta*) is the main among the different forest species. Locally it is also called Ghazari. Present sal trees are produced from coppice. After the declaration of national park, almost all the plants are extinct in this park. Conservation of species is in progress. In a survey under the SRCWP project, 369 species of plants have been identified in this park, including 25 species of climber, 111 species of shrub, 106 species of herb and 127 species of trees. 499 species of animals were also identified in the survey. Among them, 19 species of reptiles, 138 species of birds, 18 species of mammals, 11 species of amphibians and another category of fauna.

• Topography, Climate, Rainfall and Temperature:

Bhawal National Park is part of Bhawal Garh. The color of the soil here is grey, which is mainly due to the high level of acidity in the soil (pH 5.5). Temperatures range from 17.70°C to 34.300°C. The maximum temperature is 34.30°C in April and the minimum temperature is 11.700°C in January. Average annual rainfall is a minimum of 3.4 mm. in December and maximum 339 mm. in August.

• Natural Ecosystem :

A natural ecosystem is a complex network of interacting organisms and their physical environment, functioning as a cohesive unit. These systems encompass a diverse array of habitats, including forests, grasslands, wetlands, deserts, oceans, and freshwater bodies. Each ecosystem comprises biotic components (living organisms such as plants, animals, and microorganisms) and abiotic components (non-living elements like water, air, soil, and climate).

Energy flow and nutrient cycling are fundamental processes within natural ecosystems. Primary producers, mainly plants and algae, convert solar energy into chemical energy through photosynthesis. This energy then moves through the food web as herbivores consume plants, and predators consume herbivores. Decomposers, such as bacteria and fungi, break down dead organic matter, returning vital nutrients to the soil, which supports new plant growth.

Biodiversity is a critical feature of natural ecosystems, enhancing resilience and stability. High biodiversity ensures that ecosystems can withstand and recover from disturbances, such as natural disasters or human impacts. Each species plays a unique role, contributing to ecosystem services such as pollination, seed dispersal, water purification, and carbon sequestration.

Natural ecosystems also provide numerous benefits to humans, including resources like food, medicine, and raw materials. They offer recreational opportunities, aesthetic enjoyment, and cultural significance.

The preservation and restoration of natural ecosystems are vital for maintaining ecological balance and supporting life. Human activities, however, pose significant threats, including habitat destruction, pollution, and climate change. Sustainable practices and conservation efforts are essential to protect these invaluable systems for future generations.

• Aquatic Ecosystem :

Aquatic natural ecosystems encompass both freshwater and marine environments, forming a vital part of the Earth's biosphere. These ecosystems include rivers, lakes, wetlands, and groundwater systems in freshwater regions, and oceans, coral reefs, estuaries, mangrove forests, and seagrass beds in marine areas. Aquatic ecosystems are characterized by their water-based habitats, which support diverse communities of plants, animals, and microorganisms. They play essential roles in global nutrient cycling, climate regulation, and provide resources and services such as drinking water, food, and recreation. These ecosystems are also crucial for maintaining biodiversity and supporting life both in water and on land.

Freshwater ecosystem

Marine ecosystem

• **Terrestrial Ecosystem :**

A terrestrial ecosystem is a land-based community of organisms and their interactions with the environment. These ecosystems encompass a diverse array of habitats, from lush tropical rainforests and expansive grasslands to arid deserts and frigid tundras. Each type of terrestrial ecosystem is defined by its climate, geography, and the unique assemblages of plants and animals that have adapted to these conditions. Terrestrial ecosystems play a crucial role in the Earth's ecological balance, contributing to processes such as carbon cycling, soil formation, and providing habitats for a multitude of species.

Forest ecosystems are classified into several types based on their climate and geographical location. Tropical rainforests are found near the equator and are rich in biodiversity. Temperate forests have distinct seasons and include both deciduous and evergreen trees, while boreal forests (taiga), found in high northern latitudes, are dominated by coniferous trees.

Grassland ecosystems are characterized by vast open areas with grasses as the dominant vegetation and few trees. They include savannas, which are tropical with scattered trees, and temperate grasslands, which feature a mix of grasses and herbs.

Desert ecosystems are arid regions with extremely low precipitation, leading to sparse vegetation. They include hot deserts, like the Sahara, with high temperatures and cold deserts, like the Gobi, with cooler conditions.

Mountain ecosystems vary with altitude, featuring distinct zones from lush forests at lower elevations to alpine tundra at higher elevations. They support diverse plant and animal species adapted to the changing environmental conditions.

Forest ecosystem

Tundra ecosystem

Desert ecosystem

Grassland ecosystem

Mountain ecosystem

• Bhawal National Park Ecosystem :

Bhawal National Park, located in Bangladesh, showcases a diverse terrestrial ecosystem that includes tropical moist deciduous forests, grasslands, and wetlands. Spanning over 5,022 hectares, the park's primary feature is its dense forest, characterized by a mix of broadleaf trees such as Sal, Teak, and various hardwood species. These forests are rich in biodiversity, providing habitat for a variety of flora and fauna. The park's grasslands, found in open areas, support different herbivores and ground-nesting birds. These grassy patches are crucial for species like the Blackbuck, which relies on open spaces for grazing and reproduction.

Watchtower of BNP

Wetlands within the park, including ponds and seasonal marshes, are vital for sustaining aquatic life. They host a range of aquatic plants and provide breeding grounds for fish and amphibians. These wetlands also support migratory and resident bird species, adding to the park's overall biodiversity. Bhawal National Park is also home to a variety of wildlife, including the Bengal tiger, spotted deer, and a multitude of bird species.

The park's ecosystem is important for local climate regulation and conservation of biodiversity. Its rich variety of habitats supports complex ecological interactions, making it a crucial area for wildlife protection and environmental stability. The conservation of Bhawal National Park is essential for preserving its unique ecosystems and ensuring the survival of its diverse species.

Sal Forest Ecosystem

Wetland Ecosystem

• Flora and Fauna :

Bhawal National Park is basically a deciduous sal forest which is different from other forests. The main feature of this forest is that the leaves fall in winter and the leaves mix with the soil and rot to form humus, thus the soil regains its fertility. Due to the fertility of the soil, different types of fruits, forests and different types of medicinal plants are grown here along with the original sal tree. Due to climate change, global temperature is increasing, biodiversity is facing major problems. Many species of trees and wildlife have already disappeared from the park, including palash, karai, shimul. Once upon a time peacocks were seen in large numbers in Bhawal forest which are not seen anymore. Visitor birds such as Baldhen, Sarali, Hottee and Khanjan are seen in the Dhalipukur and Niklai ponds of the park area and in the lake of the park, which are playing a special role in the conservation of biodiversity as well as human entertainment. If all these resources or biodiversity are not preserved, the heritage of the country's first national park will be lost.

• Tree species of BNP :

An abundance of different plant species is observed in Bhawal National Park. The main vegetation of this forest is Shal/Gajari (*Shorea robusta*). 369 species of plants under 67 families and 147 tribes have been identified so far in this park. Among the species of plants found other than Shaal (Gajari) are Jiga, Aali, Mahogany, Akashmani, Eucalyptus, Kari, Bot, Jam, Amalaki, Haritaki, Bahera etc. Amalki, Haritki, Bahera are the favorite food of deer.

Sal tree

Gorjon tree

Eucalyptus tree

Mahogany tree

Shigun tree

Sissoo tree

Gab tree

Siris tree

• Herb, Shrub & Creeping plant species of BNP :

Shrubs include channa, cane and murta, matmatya (basil) gadila tree, dantai tree, ailya leaf, langlya vine, gila vine, painya vine, kali vine, bangkai vine.

Medicinal plants include Tunka, Palash, Lajjavati, Shatamul, Anantamul, Arjuna, Chatra Pata, Bilaichimti, Chapatya, Vajna, Olborai, Patapatlya, Shunyaalta, Khargochcha, Pelagota, Kalakucha, Hatiya Kakarol, Durba, Thankuni tree, Garlic, Chaillar Guri, Amalki. , Haritaki, Bahera, Annigota, Chutki, Ani, Monkata, Bhongul Gota, Betgota, Indrajab or Cutuj of Orissa which are used locally for diabetes, blood purification and sexual problems. Vegetables include kendua, wild potato, guichya potato, red and white potato and root potato etc

Melastoma malabathricum

Miconia nervosa

Lygodium palmatum

Paesia scaberula

Desmodium triflorum

Hypoestes strobilifera

Breynia androgyna

Curcuma flaviflora

• Animal Diversity:

Bhawal National Park is great for animal diversity useful 187 species in Bhawal National Park There is a variety of wildlife. Among these 187 species there are 139 species of birds including 18 species of mammals, 19 species of reptiles, 11 species of amphibians.

Wild boar

Small Indian civet

Monkey

• Mammals of BNP

18 species of mammals are found in Bhawal National Park. Among the mammals once abundant were tigers, antelopes which have been lost to habitat destruction and poaching although some medium and small species are abundant. Moreover, monkeys, badgers, squirrels, jackals, wild cats, wild boars are more common and porcupine and deer are less common nowadays.

Chital

Southern red muntjac

Northern plains gray langur

Indian jackal

Monkey

Indian palm squirrel

Civet

Mongoose

• Retails of BNP

Bhawal National Park is home to a diverse array of reptile species. The park's rich and varied habitats, including dense forests, wetlands, and grasslands, support a wide variety of reptiles. 19 species of reptails are found in BNP. Key species include various snakes, lizards, and turtles, each playing an essential role in the park's ecosystem. Notable reptiles found here are the Bengal Monitor (*Varanus bengalensis*), Indian Python (*Python molurus*), and various species of geckos and skinks. These reptiles contribute to the ecological balance by controlling insect and rodent populations and serving as prey for larger predators. Conservation efforts in the park aim to protect these reptilian inhabitants and their habitats from threats such as habitat destruction and poaching.

Monitor lizard

Common Krait

Oriental garden lizard

Gecko

• Amphibious of BNP

Bhawal National Park is a rich habitat for various wildlife, including a diverse array of amphibians. The park's dense forest, water bodies, and moist environment provide an ideal setting for amphibians to thrive. 11 species of amphibians are found in BNP. Among the amphibians, there are frogs, frogs, golden frogs and turtles and crabs in reservoirs. These species play a crucial role in the ecosystem by controlling insect populations and serving as bioindicators for environmental health. The park's conservation efforts aim to protect these sensitive species and their habitats, contributing to the overall biodiversity of the region.

Asian common toad

Balloon Frog

Common Tree frog

Indian Bull Frog

• Birds of BNP

Bhawal National Park, is home to a rich diversity of bird species. The park's mixed evergreen and deciduous forests, wetlands, and grasslands provide a variety of habitats that support over 139 bird species. Among these are numerous resident birds, such as the Oriental Pied Hornbill and the Greater Racket-tailed Drongo, as well as migratory species like the Asian Openbill and various types of ducks and waders. The park's birdlife contributes significantly to its ecological value and offers excellent opportunities for birdwatching and conservation studies.

Red Junglefowl

Lesser Whistling-Duck

Oriental Turtle-Dove

Asian Koel

Red-wattled Lapwing

Greater Coucal

Coppersmith Barbet

White-breasted Waterhen

• Butterflies of BNP

Bhawal National Park is renowned for its rich biodiversity, including a vibrant population of butterflies. The park's diverse flora provides an ideal habitat for these insects, making it a significant area for butterfly enthusiasts and researchers.

Example : Common Mormon (*Papilio polytes*), Blue Tiger (*Tirumala limniace*), Common Crow (*Euploea core*), Plain Tiger (*Danaus chrysippus*), Lime Butterfly (*Papilio demoleus*), Common Grass Yellow (*Eurema hecabe*), Peacock Pansy (*Junonia almana*) etc

The Bhawal National Park Butterfly Park has 47,250 butterflies of 249 species belonging to 8 genera in different stages like eggs, larvae, pupae and full-grown butterflies.

In the Checklist of Founa of Bhawal National Park Butterfly category there has included only the highest available butterflies. There are 194 species of butterfly under the 8 families of Order Lepidoptera.

Common Mormon
(*Papilio polytes*)

Blue Tiger
(*Tirumala limniace*)

Common Crow
(*Euploea core*)

Plain Tiger
(*Danaus chrysippus*)

Lime Butterfly
(*Papilio demoleus*)

Peacock Pansy
(*Junonia almana*)

Common Grass Yellow
(*Eurema hecabe*)

Swallowtail butterfly
(*Papilio machaon*)

Crimson Rose
(*Pachliopta hector*)

Great Eggfly
(*Hypolimnias bolina*)

Great Eggfly
(*Hypolimnias bolina*)

Striped Tiger
(*Danaus genutia*)

• Insects of BNP

Bhawal National Park is home to a diverse array of insects, contributing significantly to its rich biodiversity. The park hosts numerous species of dragonflies, and beetles, which play vital roles in pollination and ecosystem balance. The dense forest cover and diverse flora provide an ideal habitat for these insects.

Example : Honey Bee (*Apis mellifera*), Red Wood Ant (*Formica rufa*), Ladybug (*Coccinella septempunctata*), Common Green Darner (*Anax junius*), Japanese Beetle (*Popillia japonica*), Termite (*Reticulitermes flavipes*) etc.

This vibrant insect life enhances the ecological complexity and conservation value of Bhawal National Park.

Honey Bee
(*Apis mellifera*)

Red Wood Ant
(*Formica rufa*)

Common Green Darner
(*Anax junius*)

Praying Mantis
(*Mantis religiosa*)

• Fishes of BNP

Bhawal National Park features the Bhawal Lake, and numerous small ponds and wetlands. These water bodies support diverse aquatic species and contribute to the park's biodiversity. Seasonal streams also appear during the monsoon, enhancing the park's hydrology.

Bhawal National Park waterbodies are home to a diverse range of fish species, including Rohu (*Labeo rohita*), Catla (*Catla catla*), and Walking Catfish (*Clarias batrachus*). Other notable species include the Climbing Perch (*Anabas testudineus*) and the Spotted Snakehead (*Channa punctata*). These fish contribute significantly to the park's aquatic biodiversity and ecosystem health.

Rohu
(*Labeo rohita*)

Bighead carp
(*Aristichthys nobilis*)

Mrigal
(*Cirrhinus mrigala*)

Common carp
(*Cyprinus carpio*)

Silver carp
(*Hypophthalmichthys molitrix*)

Catla
(*Catla catla*)

• Butterfly Research Park of Bhawal National Park

butterfly research park was established in Bhawal National Park in 2007 as a joint initiative of Dhaka University Zoology Department Research Cell (EBBL-Environment Biology and Biodiversity Laboratory) and Forest Department.

In 2007, the Bangladesh Forest Department granted permission to Dhaka University to use 10 acres of land in Bhawal National Park for 10 years for various experiments and research on butterflies and butterfly-related plants. Around the park, they built a bush wall consisting of 9 species of trees. This bush wall is suitable for butterflies to live in. Inside the park, around 51,000 trees of 168 species of 35 genera, suitable for butterfly food, make 32 beds of different shapes.

The Butterfly Park has 47,250 butterflies of 249 species belonging to 8 genera in different stages like eggs, larvae, pupae and full-grown butterflies.

An open butterfly park is a natural park with a combination of three types of plants such as nectar, host and shelter plants that are suitable for butterflies to live in. "Open Butterfly Research Park" was inaugurated in Bhawal National Park on 1st June/2012. A team of thesis, M.Phil and PhD level researchers from the Department of Zoology of Dhaka University have been researching the relationship between butterflies and biodiversity for more than 12 years. At the research park, students are engaged in advanced research on butterflies. Apart from this, Pakistan is also playing a role in the development of "Ecotourism".

The researchers of this center have long been able to prove through experiments that "butterflies are bioindicators of climate change". The role of butterflies in determining the medicinal properties of plants is immense. The park is an added attraction for tourists visiting Bhawal National Park. Apart from education and research, many It is a source of joy.

• Tortoise Enclosed Breeding Centre of BNP

Funded by International Vienna Zoo and Turtle Survival Alliance of US Center, CARINAM, a joint initiative of Bangladesh and Forest Department, has practically adopted the captive breeding of Batagur turtle species in the pond adjacent to the mini zoo of Bhawal National Park. This program is supported by financial, technical and consultancy support from several other organizations and individuals. From January 2013, the tortoise breeding program was transferred from Karanam to IUCN Bangladesh. Bangladesh Nature and Life Foundation is acting as the media partner for this event. The Forest Department handed over the Batagur baska breeding project in 2010 to two ponds adjacent to the mini zoo in Bhawal National Park.

At present, the total number of full-grown tortoises of large kaitta species in Batagur project of Bhawal National Park is 20. Among them 14 males, 6 females, 106 live tortoises of different ages. Currently research on 4 tortoises of Hadella and Morinia species in progress.

• Gharial Conservation Centre of BNP

Gharial is fast disappearing from Bangladesh. Gharial is now almost extinct due to decrease in navigability of rivers, decrease in water flow and pollution etc. Gharials are still occasionally caught in fishermen's nets in the Padma River. About 2 extinct gharials of Bangladesh are currently being preserved in ponds in Bhawal National Park. The view of Gharial's sunshine on the banks of the pond is very attractive to tourists.

• **Challenges of the Natural Ecosystem and Biodiversity of BNP .**

Bhawal National Park (BNP) faces several challenges impacting its natural ecosystem and biodiversity. Here are some of the key challenges :

Deforestation and Habitat Loss: Illegal logging and land encroachment for agricultural and urban development reduce forest cover, leading to habitat loss for many species.

Poaching and Illegal Wildlife Trade: Poaching of wildlife for trade and subsistence hunting threatens the park's biodiversity, particularly targeting endangered species.

Invasive Species: Non-native species can outcompete, prey on, or bring diseases to native species, disrupting the ecological balance.

Pollution: Industrial and agricultural runoff, along with littering, can contaminate water bodies and soil, negatively affecting flora and fauna.

Climate Change: Changes in temperature and precipitation patterns can alter habitats and food availability, putting stress on wildlife and plant species.

Human-Wildlife Conflict: As human populations grow near the park, encounters between people and wildlife increase, leading to potential conflicts and threats to both humans and animals.

Forest Fires: Accidental or deliberate fires can devastate large areas of the park, destroying habitats and reducing biodiversity.

Resource Exploitation: Overharvesting of forest resources such as timber, fuelwood, and non-timber forest products can deplete natural resources and harm the ecosystem.

Tourism Pressure: Unregulated tourism can lead to habitat degradation, pollution, and disturbance to wildlife.

Efforts to address these challenges include stricter law enforcement, habitat restoration projects, community involvement in conservation, and public awareness campaigns.

• **Strategies to overcome the challenges of biodiversity of BNP**

Overcoming the challenges to the natural ecosystem and biodiversity of Bhawal National Park (BNP) requires a multifaceted approach involving various stakeholders. Here are some strategies:

Strengthen Law Enforcement:Increase patrolling and monitoring to prevent illegal logging, poaching, and encroachment.Implement stricter penalties for environmental crimes.

Habitat Restoration:Reforestation and afforestation programs to restore degraded areas.Removal of invasive species and reintroduction of native species.

Community Involvement:Engage local communities in conservation efforts through education and awareness programs.Provide alternative livelihoods to reduce dependence on forest resources.Establish community-based monitoring and protection initiatives.

Pollution Control:Implement waste management systems to reduce littering and pollution.Regulate agricultural and industrial runoff through sustainable practices and buffer zones.

Climate Change Mitigation:Develop and implement climate adaptation strategies for wildlife and habitats.Promote sustainable land use and water management practices.

Human-Wildlife Conflict Management:Create buffer zones between human settlements and wildlife habitats.Implement early warning systems and mitigation measures to prevent conflicts.Provide compensation and support to affected communities.

Fire Management:Develop fire management plans, including prevention, early detection, and rapid response.Educate local communities about the dangers of forest fires and safe practices.

Sustainable Resource Use:Promote sustainable harvesting of forest resources.Encourage the use of alternative energy sources to reduce dependence on fuelwood.

Regulate Tourism:Develop eco-friendly tourism guidelines and infrastructure.Limit the number of visitors to sensitive areas and enforce regulations to minimize impact.

Research and Monitoring:Conduct regular biodiversity assessments and ecological monitoring.Use data to inform conservation strategies and adaptive management practices.

• Overview of flora and fauna checklist of Bhawal National Park (BNP)

Category	Total Families	Total Species
Flora		
Tree	67	121
Shrub	44	111
Herb	41	106
Climber	13	25
Fauna		
Bird	55	138
Amphibian	6	11
Mammal	13	18
Reptile	9	19
Butterfly	8	194
Insect	31	61
fish	23	58

127 Tree
111 Shrub
106 herb
25 Climber

Flora of

369 species of plants under
67 families &
147 tribes

Bhawal National Park

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
Tree species			
1	Sal	<i>Shorea robusta</i>	Dipterocarpaceae
2	Garjan	<i>Dipterocarpus indicus</i>	
3	Telsur	<i>Hopea odorata</i>	
4	Champa	<i>Magnolia champaca</i>	MAGNOLIOPSIDA
5	Ata	<i>Annona squamosa</i>	ANNONACEAE
6	Nona	<i>A. reticulata</i>	
7	Fonseti	<i>Alphonsea lutea</i>	
8	Gandhi gajari	<i>Milium velutina</i>	
9	Debdaru	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	
10	Mota pasuti	<i>Knema cinerea</i>	MYRISTICACEAE
11	Modon mosta	<i>Actinodaphne gullavara</i>	LAURACEAE
12	Tejpata	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>	
13	Modon-mosto	<i>Dehaasia kurzii</i>	
14	Baro kukurchita	<i>Litsea monopetala</i>	
15	Dulia	<i>Ocotea lancifolia</i>	
16	Bativa	<i>Meliosma pinnata</i>	SABIACEAE
17	Dibru	<i>M. simplicifolia</i>	
18	Banjiga	<i>Trema orientalis</i>	ULMACEAE
19	Dolia sat	<i>Poikilospermum suaveolens</i>	CECROPIACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family	
20	Chapalish	<i>Artocarpus chama</i>	MORACEAE	
21	Kanthal	<i>A. heterophyllus</i>		
22	Deua	<i>A. lacucha</i>		
23	Bot	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>		
24	Pakur	<i>F. benjamina</i>		
25	<i>Rubber gach</i>	<i>F. elastic</i>		
26	Jagyadumur	<i>F. racemosa</i>		
27	Ashwath	<i>F. religiosa</i>		
28	Sadimadi dumur	<i>F. semicordata</i>		
29	Bichitrabat	<i>F. variegata</i>		
30	Sheora	<i>Streblus asper</i>		
31	Horhutta	<i>Oreocnide integrifolia</i>		URTICACEAE
32	Marich	<i>Sarcochlamys pulcherrima</i>		
33	Jhumka bhadi	<i>Engelhardia spicata</i>	JUGLANDACEAE	
34	Batna	<i>Quercus obtusata</i>	FAGACEAE	
35	Chalta	<i>Dillenia indica</i>	DILLENIACEAE	
36	Ban chalta	<i>D. pentagyna</i>		
37	Bonak	<i>Schima wallichii</i>	THEACEAE	
38	Dalup	<i>Saurauia roxburghii</i>	ACTINIDIACEAE	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
39	Cowa	<i>Garcinia cowa</i>	CLUSIACEAE
40	Nagessawar	<i>Mesua ferrea</i>	
41	Petipai	<i>Elaeocarpus petiolatus</i>	ELAEOCARPACEAE
42	Pichandi	<i>Grewia nervosa</i>	TILIACEAE
43	Jonli pholsa	<i>G. tiliifolia</i>	
44	Kanackchampa	<i>Pterosprum acerifolium</i>	STERCULIACEAE
45	Udal	<i>Sterculia villosa</i>	
46	Simul	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	BOMBACACEAE
47	Udal	<i>Hibiscus macrophyllus</i>	MALVACEAE
48	Hijol	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i>	LECYTHIDACEAE
49	Lukluki	<i>Flacourtia jangomas</i>	
50	Pape	<i>Carica papaya</i>	CARICACEAE
51	Mohua	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	SAPOTACEAE
52	Bokul	<i>Mimusops elengi</i>	
53	Deshi gab	<i>Diospyros malabarica</i>	EBENACEAE
54	Kumjomeva	<i>Styrax serrulatus</i>	STYRACACEAE
55	Barabahuri	<i>Symplocos macrophylla</i>	SYMPLOCACEAE
56	Banglauni	<i>Maesa bengalensis</i>	PRIMULACEAE
57	Ceylon cherry	<i>Prunus ceylanica</i>	ROSACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
58	Akashmoni	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i>	MIMOSACEAE
59	Mangium	<i>A. mangium</i>	
60	Bandar lathi	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	CAESALPINIACEAE
61	Kuishnachura	<i>Delonix regia</i>	
62	Minjiri	<i>Senna siamea</i>	
63	Tetul	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	FABACEAE
64	Korai	<i>Derris robusta</i>	
65	Bahari mander	<i>Erythrina variegata</i>	
66	Bandorhola	<i>Duabanga grandiflora</i>	SONNERATIACEAE
67	Jarul	<i>Lagerstroemia speciosa</i>	LYTHRACEAE
68	Agar	<i>Aquilaria agallocha</i>	THYMELAEACEAE
69	Eucalyptus	<i>Corymbia citriodora</i>	MYRTACEAE
70	Peyara	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	
71	Kaloram	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	
72	Ban Jam	<i>S. fruticosum</i>	
73	Dhaki Jam	<i>S. grande</i>	
74	Arjun	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	COMBRETACEAE
75	Bohera	<i>T. bellirica</i>	
76	Kathbadam	<i>T. catappa</i>	
77	Horitoki	<i>T. chebula</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
78	Rascow	<i>Carallia brachiata</i>	RHIZOPHORACEAE
79	Madhu-phal	<i>Bhesa robusta</i>	CELASTRACEAE
80	Kokua	<i>Aporosa wallichii</i>	EUPHORBIACEAE
81	Kainjal	<i>Bischofia javanica</i>	
82	Latkan	<i>Baccaurea ramiflora</i>	
83	Dhala kakua	<i>Chaetocarpus castanocarpus</i>	
84	Gulle	<i>Macaranga indica</i>	
85	Amloki	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	
86	Ban naranga	<i>Suregada multiflora</i>	
87	Bol boroi	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	
88	Bhola	<i>Turpinia pomifera</i>	STAPHYLEACEAE
89	Lichu	<i>Litchi chinensis</i>	SAPINDACEAE
90	Paharijiga	<i>Garuga pinnata</i>	BURSERACEAE
91	Kaju	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	ANACARDIACEAE
92	Jiga	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i>	
93	Aam	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	
94	Jangli aam	<i>M. sylvatica.</i>	
95	Jaowa	<i>Holigarna caustica</i>	
96	Kakuasingh	<i>Rhus succedanea</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
97	Pitraj	<i>Aphanamixis polystachya</i>	MELIACEAE
98	Neem	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	
99	Mahogini	<i>Swietenia mahagoni</i>	
100	Bara mahogoni	<i>S. macrophylla</i>	
101	Rata	<i>Dysoxylum gotadhora</i>	
102	Toon	<i>Toona ciliata</i>	
103	Bonlichu	<i>Walsura robusta</i>	
104	Bel	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	RUTACEAE
105	Dulia	<i>Micromelum minutum</i>	
106	Bilimbi	<i>Averrhoa bilimbi</i>	OXALIDACEAE
107	Kamranga	<i>A. carambola</i>	
108	Kurila	<i>Brassaiopsis glomerulata</i>	ARALIACEAE
109	Argoja	<i>Trevesia palmata</i>	
110	Chhatim	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	APOCYNACEAE
111	Boula	<i>Cordia dichotoma</i>	BORAGINACEAE
112	Barmala	<i>Callicarpa arborea</i>	LAMIACEAE
113	Shegun	<i>Tectona grandis</i>	OLEACEAE
114	Nishinda	<i>Vitex negundo</i>	
115	Awal	<i>V. peduncularis</i>	
116	Seliawal	<i>V. pinnata</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
117	Awal	<i>Stereospermum tetragonum</i>	BIGNONIACEAE
118	Sitgach	<i>Gardenia coronaria</i>	RUBIACEAE
119	Jangli basok	<i>Morinda angustifolia</i>	
120	Dakrom	<i>Mitragyna parviflora</i>	
121	Kadam	<i>Neolamarckia cadamba</i>	
122	Tulaload	<i>Wendlandia grandis</i>	
123	Supari	<i>Areca catechu</i>	ARECACEAE
124	Tal	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i>	
125	Chau-gota	<i>Caryota urens</i>	
126	Narikel	<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	
127	Deshi khejur	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
Shrub species			
1	Kulla	<i>Dasymaschalon longiflorum</i>	ANNONACEAE
2	Rantas	<i>Chloranthus erectus</i>	CHLORANTHACEAE
3	Kadsuta	<i>Kadsura heteroclita</i>	SCHISANDRACEAE
4	Henalora	<i>Pycnarrhena planiflora</i>	MENISPERMACEAE
5	Padma gulancha	<i>Tinospora sinensis</i>	URTICACEAE
6	Borthurthuri	<i>Boehmeria glomerulifera</i>	
7	Ulichara	<i>B. macrophylla</i>	
8	Chutra	<i>Dendrocnide sinuata</i>	
9	Glabrum	<i>Pilea glaberrima</i>	
10	Bagan bilash	<i>Bougainvillea spectabilis</i>	NYCTAGINACEAE
11	Sagoler bori	<i>Eurya acuminata</i>	THEACEAE
12	Pichandi	<i>Grewia serrulata</i>	TILIACEAE
13	Ulatkambal	<i>Abroma augusta</i>	STERCULIACEAE
14	Jaba	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i>	MALVACEAE
15	Ram bhindi	<i>H. surattensis</i>	
16	Marich jaba	<i>Malvaviscus arboreus</i>	
17	Banghagra	<i>Urena lobata</i>	
18	Bauchi	<i>Flacourtia indica</i>	FLACOURTIACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
19	Mathua	<i>Ardisia sanguinolenta</i>	PRIMULACEAE
20	Bakul lata	<i>Embelia ribes</i>	
21	Bhau jawa	<i>Hymenandra wallichii</i>	
22	Gangu lata	<i>Maesa chisia</i>	
23	Sesu	<i>M. indica</i>	
24	Noa-maricha	<i>M. ramentacea</i>	
25	Hirachura	<i>Rubus hexagynus</i>	ROSACEAE
26	Kata golap	<i>Rosa chinensis</i>	
27	Lajjaboti	<i>Mimosa pudica</i>	MIMOSACEAE
28	Nata	<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i>	CAESALPINIACEAE
29	Dadmardan	<i>Senna alata</i>	
30	Kalkashunda	<i>S. sophora</i>	
31	Orhor	<i>Cajanus scarabaeoides</i>	FABACEAE
32	Gupuri	<i>Dalhousiea bracteata</i>	
33	Karpo modi	<i>D. heterocarpon</i>	
34	Laximodi	<i>D. laxiflorum</i>	
35	Kanimanda	<i>Tadehagi triquetrum</i>	
36	Vuluk phan	<i>Flemingia involucrata</i>	
37	Baro salpan	<i>F. macrophylla</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
38	Chingri pata	<i>F. strobilifera</i>	FABACEAE
39	Gerina nil	<i>Indigofera zollingeriana</i>	
40	Diangleja	<i>Uraria crinita</i>	
41	Mendi	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	LYTHRACEAE
42	Ban tejpatha	<i>Melastoma malabathricum</i>	MELASTOMATACEAE
43	Nepaligachi	<i>Osbeckia nepalensis</i>	
44	Patyuni	<i>Combretum acuminatum</i>	COMBRETACEAE
45	Capsul gach	<i>Olox acuminata</i>	OLACACEAE
46	Xanthric	<i>Helixanthera parasitica</i>	LORANTHACEAE
47	Chota banda	<i>Macrosolen cochinchinensis</i>	
48	Pargacha	<i>Scurrula parasitica</i>	
49	Vesa	<i>Salacia chinensis</i>	HIPPOCRATEACEAE
50	Raktim	<i>Ilex godajam</i>	AQUIFOLIACEAE
51	Lalsa	<i>Actephila excelsa</i>	EUPHORBIACEAE
52	Alkotil	<i>Alchornea tiliifolia</i>	
53	Titij am	<i>Antidesma acidum</i>	
54	Shial buka	<i>A. montanum</i>	
55	Khoi	<i>Bridelia tomentosa</i>	
56	Chutra	<i>Cnesmone javanica</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
57	Chuka	<i>Baliospermum solanifolium</i>	EUPHORBIACEAE
58	Aniatori	<i>Glochidion multiloculare</i>	
59	Pankushi	<i>Phyllanthus reticulatus</i>	
60	Bherenda	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	
61	Mithapotro	<i>Sauropus androgynus</i>	
62	Herjengota	<i>Gouania tiliifolia</i>	RHAMNACEAE
63	Ban boroi	<i>Ziziphus. oenopolia</i>	
64	Kurkurjhibba	<i>Leea indica</i>	LEEACEAE
65	Horina lata	<i>Tetrastigma leucostaphylum</i>	VITACEAE
66	Chita	<i>Allophylus cobbe</i>	SAPINDACEAE
67	Tapir	<i>Pegia nitida</i>	ANACARDIACEAE
68	Bon jamir	<i>Acronychia pedunculata</i>	RUTACEAE
69	Pani lebu	<i>Citrus medica</i>	
70	Datmajani	<i>Glycosmis pentaphylla</i>	
71	Curry pata	<i>Murraya koenigii</i>	
72	Bilati dhania	<i>Eryngium foetidum</i>	APIACEAE
73	Neemda	<i>Buddleja asiatica</i>	BUDDLEJACEAE
74	Kurchi	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i>	APOCYNACEAE
75	Tagar	<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
76	Dhutra	<i>Datura metel</i>	SOLANACEAE
77	Dhol kolmi	<i>Ipomoea carnea</i>	CONVOLVULACEAE
78	Kutuskanta	<i>Lantana camara</i>	VERBENACEAE
79	Lamarck	<i>Callicarpa longifolia</i>	LAMIACEAE
80	Bamunhatti	<i>Clerodendrum indicum</i>	
81	Bhat	<i>C. infortunatum</i>	
82	Mali bong	<i>C. laevifolium</i>	
83	Ram tulsi	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i>	
84	Bamanhati	<i>Rothea serrata</i>	
85	Beli	<i>Jasminum sambac</i>	OLEACEAE
86	Jua	<i>J. scandens</i>	
89	Lalong	<i>Premna esculenta</i>	
90	Kastacha	<i>Acanthus leucostachyus</i>	ACANTHACEAE
91	Khara murali	<i>Eranthemum strictum</i>	
92	Bashak	<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	
93	Agnilora	<i>Phlogacanthus curviflorus</i>	
94	Rambasak	<i>P. thyrsiformis</i>	
95	Agnibasak	<i>P. tubiflorus</i>	
96	Mankanta	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i>	RUBIACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family	
97	Nata rangan	<i>Ixora acuminata</i>	RUBIACEAE	
98	Rangan	<i>I. coccinea</i>		
100	Ganghalrangan	<i>I. pavetta</i>		
101	Shum rangan	<i>I. spectabilis</i>		
102	Sony lasi	<i>Lasianthus chrysoneurus</i>		
103	Sil daura	<i>Mussaenda roxburghii</i>		
104	Nagabali	<i>M. frondosa</i>		
104	Baropata	<i>M. macrophylla</i>		
105	muchenda	<i>Mussaenda sp.</i>		
106	Mycetelon	<i>Mycetia longifolia</i>		
107	Natanuran	<i>Myrioneuron nutans</i>		
108	Murta	<i>Schumannianthus dichotomus</i>		MARANTACEAE
109	Shatamuli	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>		LILIACEAE
110	Kado drakan	<i>Dracaena spicata</i>	AGAVACEAE	
111	Keya kanta	<i>Pandanus foetidus</i>	PANDANACEAE	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
Herb Species			
1	Pithapata	<i>Peperomia pellucida</i>	PIPERACEAE
2	Pipul	<i>P. longum</i>	
3	Ban pan	<i>P. sylvaticum</i>	
4	Iswararmul	<i>Aristolochia tagala</i>	ARISTOLOCHIACEAE
5	Nilshapla	<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>	NYMPHAEACEAE
6	Lal shapla	<i>N. rubra</i>	
7	Sheola	<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i>	CERATOPHYLLACEAE
8	Akanadi	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	MENISPERMACEAE
9	Patalpur	<i>Cyclea barbata</i>	
10	Sonatola	<i>Diploclisia glaucescens</i>	
11	Goria lata	<i>Pericampylus glaucus</i>	
12	Nimukha	<i>Stephania japonica</i>	
13	Sajba lat	<i>Sabia lanceolata</i>	SABIACEAE
14	Bhui dumur	<i>Ficus pumila</i>	MORACEAE
15	Karat-bot	<i>F. sagittata</i>	
16	Clarkejhara	<i>Elatostema clarkei</i>	URTICACEAE
17	Lal bichuti	<i>Laportea interrupta</i>	
18	Kullaruki	<i>Pouzolzia zeylanica</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
19	Punarnava	<i>Boerhavia defusa</i>	NYCTAGINACEAE
20	Bathua shak	<i>Chenopodium album</i>	CHENOPODIACEAE
21	Apang	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	AMARANTHACEAE
22	Jhuli khata	<i>Alternanthera paronychioides</i>	
23	Henchi	<i>A. philoxeroides</i>	
24	Malancha	<i>A. sessilis</i>	
25	Kantanotey	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	
26	Notey shak	<i>A. viridis</i>	
27	Shyontula	<i>Cyathula prostrata</i>	
28	Biskatali	<i>Persicaria hydropiper</i>	POLYGONACEAE
29	Raniphul	<i>Polygonum effusum</i>	
30	Panibishkatali	<i>P. lapathifolium</i>	
31	Bon-palang	<i>Rumex maritimus</i>	
32	Lata chalta	<i>Tetracera sarmentosa</i>	DILLENIACEAE
33	Sagoler bori	<i>Eurya acuminata</i>	THEACEAE
34	Titapat	<i>Corchorus aestuans</i>	TILIACEAE
35	Bon okua	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i>	
36	Plofetta	<i>T. pilosa</i>	
37	Tiki-okua	<i>Melochia corchorifolia</i>	STERCULIACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
38	Mushak-dana	<i>Abelmoschus moschatus</i>	MALVACEAE
39	Petari	<i>Abutilon indicum</i>	
40	Kureta	<i>Sida acuta</i>	
41	Jumka	<i>S. cordata</i>	
42	Lal berela	<i>S. rhombifolia</i>	
43	Akandaphal	<i>Adenia trilobata</i>	PASSILORACEAE
44	Telakucha	<i>Coccinia grandis</i>	CUCURBITACEAE
45	Gymnopada	<i>Gynostemma pentaphyllum</i>	
46	Dhundal	<i>Luffa cylindrica</i>	
47	Karola	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	
48	Ghee korolla	<i>M. dioica</i>	
49	Bilari	<i>Mukia maderaspatana</i>	
50	Makal	<i>Trichosanthes tricuspidata</i>	
51	Gonibata	<i>Begonia annulata</i>	BEGONIACEAE
52	Gonorakto	<i>B. roxburghii</i>	
53	Madhumaloti	<i>Stixis suaveolens</i>	CAPPARACEAE
54	Bansarisha	<i>Rorippa indica</i>	BRASSICACEAE
55	Terasena	<i>Senna tora</i>	CAESALPINIACEAE
56	Dadbari	<i>Dalbergia stipulacea</i>	FABACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
57	Bon motorsuti	<i>Desmodium heterophyllum</i>	FABACEAE
58	Khesari	<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>	
59	Alkushi	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	
60	Mugi kunch	<i>Pueraria phaseoloides</i>	
61	Pan lata	<i>Spatholobus parviflorus</i>	
62	Bilakshani	<i>Tephrosia candida</i>	
63	Maskalay	<i>Vigna mungo</i>	
64	Acidpata	<i>Ammannia multiflora</i>	LYTHRACEAE
65	Deshi ghurni	<i>Rotala indica</i>	
66	Dim ghurni	<i>R. rotundifolia</i>	
67	Bhuikura	<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i>	ONAGRACEAE
68	Amorkura	<i>L. perennis</i>	
69	Kaligaichi	<i>Combretum roxburghii</i>	COMBRETACEAE
70	Yunanlata	<i>C. wallichii</i>	
71	Muktajhuri	<i>Acalypha indica</i>	EUPHORBIACEAE
72	Banmarich	<i>Croton bonplandianus</i>	
73	Bara dudhia	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	
74	Bhuiamla	<i>Phyllanthus niruri</i>	
75	Hazarmani	<i>P. urinaria</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
76	Gowalia lata	<i>Ampelocissus latifolia</i>	VITACEAE
77	Japani goali lata	<i>Cayratia japonica</i>	
78	Amal lata	<i>Cayratia trifolia</i>	
80	Meradu	<i>Polygala chinensis</i>	POLYGALACEAE
81	Teradudhi	<i>P. erioptera</i>	
82	Amrul	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	OXALIDACEAE
83	Thankuni	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	APIACEAE
84	Gimashak	<i>Hydrocotyle sibthorpioides</i>	
85	Ban tamak	<i>Nicotiana plumbaginifolia</i>	SOLANACEAE
86	Gota begun	<i>Solanum torvum</i>	
87	Kolmishak	<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i>	CONVOLVULACEAE
88	Chadmala	<i>Nymphoides hydrophylla</i>	MENYANTHACEAE
89	Hatisur	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i>	BORAGINACEAE
90	Kalomegh	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	ACANTHACEAE
91	Bish lata	<i>Hedyotis scandens</i>	RUBIACEAE
92	Helencha	<i>Enhydra fluctuans</i>	ASTERACEAE
93	Assam lata	<i>Mikania micrantha</i>	
94	Jangli kachu	<i>Colocasia esculenta</i>	ARACEAE
95	Kachuripana	<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i>	PONTEDERIACEAE

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
96	Deotara	<i>Alpinia malaccensis</i>	ZINGIBERACEAE
97	Ban haldi	<i>Curcuma aromatica</i>	
98	Kala holdi	<i>C. caesia</i>	
99	Shoti	<i>C. phacocaulis</i>	
100	Dhaki globba	<i>Globba bracteolata</i>	
101	Maran globba	<i>G. marantina</i>	
102	Shukh globba	<i>G. multiflora</i>	
103	Dolon chapa	<i>Hedychium coronarium</i>	
104	Pala ada	<i>H. thyriforme</i>	
105	Ada	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	
106	Bon ada	<i>Z. zerumbet</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
Climber Species			
1	Shotomuli	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Asparagaceae
2	Nata karanj	<i>Bauhinia vahlii Wight</i>	Fabaceae
3	Bidipata	<i>Caesalpinia bonducella</i>	
4	Bish lata	<i>Millettia pachycarpa</i>	
5	Bet	<i>Calamus tenuis</i>	Arecaceae
6	Paniyalata	<i>Cissus adnata</i>	Vitaceae
7	Germanlata	<i>Melothria maderaspatana</i>	
8	Keoyakanthal	<i>Coccinia cordifolia</i>	Cucurbitaceae
9	Telakuha	<i>Coccinia grandis</i>	
10	Makal	<i>Trichosanthes bracteata</i>	
11	Metaalu	<i>Dioscorea alata</i>	Dioscoreaceae
12	Bishalu	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i>	
13	Jhumalu	<i>Dioscorea hispida</i>	
14	Shuorialu	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i>	
15	Dumurlata	<i>Dioscorea tomentosa</i>	
16	Kalidudhi	<i>Ficus scandens</i>	Moraceae
17	Patilalau	<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i>	Apocynaceae
18	Assamlata	<i>Mikania cordata</i>	Asteraceae
19	Chai Kalalata	<i>Mikania micrantha</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
20	Harjora lata	<i>Byttneria pilosa</i>	STERCULIACEAE
21	Dukhu lata	<i>Cissus javana</i>	VITACEAE
22	Bhatia lata	<i>C. adnata</i>	
23	Nimakumina	<i>Gymnema acuminatum</i>	ASCLEPIADACEAE
24	Hatilata	<i>Pothos scandens</i>	ARACEAE
25	Money plant	<i>Epipremnum aureum</i>	

Fauna of Bhawal National Park

Bird
138 Species

Mammal
18 Species

Amphibian
11 Species

Reptile
19 Species

Butterflie
194 species

• Checklist of Bird Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
1	Fulvous Whistling-Duck	<i>Dendrocygna bicolor</i>	Anatidae
2	Lesser Whistling-Duck	<i>Dendrocygna javanica</i>	
3	Oriental Turtle-Dove	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i>	Columbidae
4	Eurasian Collared-Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	
5	Red Collared-Dove	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	
6	Spotted Dove	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i>	
7	Yellow-footed Green-Pigeon	<i>Treron phoenicopterus</i>	
8	Greater Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Cuculidae
9	Green-billed Malkoha	<i>Phaenicophaeus tristis</i>	
10	Asian Koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopaceus</i>	
11	Plaintive Cuckoo	<i>Cacomantis merulinus</i>	
12	Large Hawk-Cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx sparverioides</i>	
13	Common Hawk-Cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	
14	Indian Cuckoo	<i>Cuculus micropterus</i>	
15	Large-tailed Nightjar	<i>Caprimulgus macrurus</i>	Caprimulgidae
16	House Swift	<i>Apus nipalensis</i>	Apodidae
17	Asian Palm Swift	<i>Cypsiurus balasiensis</i>	
18	Crested Treeswift	<i>Hemiprocne coronata</i>	Hemiprocnidae

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
19	White-breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	Rallidae
20	Yellow-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus malabaricus</i>	Charadriidae
21	Gray-headed Lapwing	<i>Vanellus cinereus</i>	
22	Red-wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	
23	Bronze-winged Jacana	<i>Metopidius indicus</i>	Jacanidae
24	Green Sandpiper	<i>Tringa ochropus</i>	Scolopacidae
25	Asian Openbill	<i>Anastomus oscitans</i>	Ciconiidae
26	Little Cormorant	<i>Microcarbo niger</i>	Phalacrocoracidae
27	Black-crowned Night Heron	<i>Nycticorax nycticorax</i>	Ardeidae
28	Little Egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	
29	Striated Heron	<i>Butorides striata</i>	
30	Indian Pond-Heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	
31	Eastern Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus coromandus</i>	
32	Great Egret	<i>Ardea alba</i>	
33	Black-winged Kite	<i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	Accipitridae
34	Oriental Honey-buzzard	<i>Pernis ptilorhynchus</i>	
35	Black Baza	<i>Aviceda leuphotes</i>	
36	Crested Serpent-Eagle	<i>Spilornis cheela</i>	
37	Changeable Hawk-Eagle	<i>Nisaetus cirrhatus</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
38	Greater Spotted Eagle	<i>Clanga clanga</i>	Accipitridae
39	White-eyed Buzzard	<i>Butastur teesa</i>	
40	Shikra	<i>Accipiter badius</i>	
41	Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	
42	Brahminy Kite	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	
43	Gray-headed Fish-Eagle	<i>Icthyophaga ichthyaetus</i>	
44	Barn Owl	<i>Tyto alba</i>	Tytonidae
45	Collared Scops-Owl	<i>Otus lettia</i>	Strigidae
46	Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	
47	Brown Boobook	<i>Ninox scutulata</i>	
48	Eurasian Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	Upupidae
49	Common Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	Alcedinidae
50	Stork-billed Kingfisher	<i>Pelargopsis capensis</i>	
51	White-throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	
52	Pied Kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudis</i>	
53	Asian Green Bee-eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Meropidae
54	Blue-tailed Bee-eater	<i>Merops philippinus</i>	
55	Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Psilopogon haemacephalus</i>	Megalaimidae
56	Lineated Barbet	<i>Psilopogon lineatus</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
57	Blue-throated Barbet	<i>Psilopogon asiaticus</i>	Megalaimidae
58	Fulvous-breasted Woodpecker	<i>Dendrocopos macei</i>	Picidae
59	Greater Flameback	<i>Chrysocolaptes guttacristatus</i>	
60	Rufous Woodpecker	<i>Micropternus brachyurus</i>	
61	Black-rumped Flameback	<i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	
62	Streak-throated Woodpecker	<i>Picus xanthopygaeus</i>	
63	Gray-headed Woodpecker	<i>Picus canus</i>	
64	Indian Pitta	<i>Pitta brachyura</i>	Psittaculidae
65	Small Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus cinnamomeus</i>	Campephagidae
66	Scarlet Minivet	<i>Pericrocotus speciosus</i>	
67	Large Cuckooshrike	<i>Coracina macei</i>	
68	Black-winged Cuckooshrike	<i>Lalage melaschistos</i>	
69	Black-headed Cuckooshrike	<i>Lalage melanoptera</i>	
70	Black-naped Oriole	<i>Oriolus chinensis</i>	Oriolidae
71	Black-hooded Oriole	<i>Oriolus xanthornus</i>	
72	Ashy Woodswallow	<i>Artamus fuscus</i>	Artamidae
73	Large Woodshrike	<i>Tephrodornis virgatus</i>	Vangidae
74	Common Woodshrike	<i>Tephrodornis pondicerianus</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
75	Common Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	Aegithinidae
76	White-throated Fantail	<i>Rhipidura albicollis</i>	Rhipiduridae
78	Black Drongo	<i>Dicrurus macrocercus</i>	Dicruridae
79	Ashy Drongo	<i>Dicrurus leucophaeus</i>	
80	Bronzed Drongo	<i>Dicrurus aeneus</i>	
81	Hair-crested Drongo	<i>Dicrurus hottentottus</i>	
82	Short-tailed Drongo	<i>Dicrurus striatus</i>	
83	Spangled Drongo	<i>Dicrurus bracteatus</i>	
84	Black-naped Monarch	<i>Hypothymis azurea</i>	Monarchidae
85	Brown Shrike	<i>Lanius cristatus</i>	Laniidae
86	Long-tailed Shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i>	
87	Gray-backed Shrike	<i>Lanius tephronotus</i>	
88	Rufous Treepie	<i>Dendrocitta vagabunda</i>	Corvidae
89	House Crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	
90	Large-billed Crow	<i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	
91	Gray-headed Canary-Flycatcher	<i>Culicicapa ceylonensis</i>	Stenostiridae
92	Cinereous Tit	<i>Parus cinereus</i>	Paridae
93	Bengal Bushlark	<i>Mirafra assamica</i>	Alaudidae
94	Blyth's Reed Warbler	<i>Acrocephalus dumetorum</i>	Acrocephalidae

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
95	Common Tailorbird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	Cisticolidae
96	Gray-breasted Prinia	<i>Prinia hodgsonii</i>	
97	Plain Prinia	<i>Prinia inornata</i>	
98	Barn Swallow	<i>Hirundo rustica</i>	Hirundinidae
99	Red-rumped Swallow	<i>Cecropis daurica</i>	
100	Red-whiskered Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	Pycnonotidae
101	Red-vented Bulbul	<i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	
102	Yellow-browed Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus inornatus</i>	Phylloscopidae
103	Dusky Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus fuscatus</i>	
103	Green-crowned Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus burkii</i>	
104	Greenish Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus trochiloides</i>	
105	Blyth's Leaf Warbler	<i>Phylloscopus reguloides</i>	
106	Indian White-eye	<i>Zosterops palpebrosus</i>	Zosteropidae
107	Pin-striped Tit-Babbler	<i>Mixornis gularis</i>	Timaliidae
108	Abbott's Babbler	<i>Malacocincla abbotti</i>	Pellorneidae
109	Jungle Babbler	<i>Argya striata</i>	Leiothrichidae
110	Striated Babbler	<i>Argya earlei</i>	
111	Indian Pied Starling	<i>Gracupica contra</i>	Sturnidae
112	Brahminy Starling	<i>Sturnia pagodarum</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
113	Chestnut-tailed Starling	<i>Sturnia malabarica</i>	Sturnidae
114	Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	
115	Jungle Myna	<i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	
116	Scaly Thrush	<i>Zoothera dauma</i>	Turdidae
117	Orange-headed Thrush	<i>Geokichla citrina</i>	
118	Tickell's Thrush	<i>Turdus unicolor</i>	
119	Oriental Magpie-Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	Muscicapidae
120	White-rumped Shama	<i>Copsychus malabaricus</i>	
121	Taiga Flycatcher	<i>Ficedula albicilla</i>	
122	Blue Rock-Thrush	<i>Monticola solitarius</i>	
123	Pale-billed Flowerpecker	<i>Dicaeum erythrorhynchos</i>	Dicaeidae
124	Purple-rumped Sunbird	<i>Leptocoma zeylonica</i>	Nectariniidae
125	Purple Sunbird	<i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	
126	Indian Silverbill	<i>Euodice malabarica</i>	Estrildidae
127	Scaly-breasted Munia	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	
128	Tricolored Munia	<i>Lonchura malacca</i>	
129	Chestnut Munia	<i>Lonchura atricapilla</i>	
130	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Passeridae
131	Black-faced Bunting	<i>Emberiza spodocephala</i>	Emberizidae

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
132	Gray Wagtail	<i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	Motacillidae
133	Eastern Yellow Wagtail	<i>Motacilla tschutschensis</i>	
134	Citrine Wagtail	<i>Motacilla citreola</i>	
135	White-browed Wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	
136	White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	
137	Paddyfield Pipit	<i>Anthus rufulus</i>	
138	Olive-backed Pipit	<i>Anthus hodgsoni</i>	

• Checklist of Amphibian Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
1	Common Toad	<i>Duttaphrynus melanostictus</i>	Bufonidae
2	Asian Common Toad	<i>Duttaphrynus stuartii</i>	
3	Sticky Frog	<i>Kalophrynus interlineatus</i>	Microhylidae
4	Berdmore's Microhylid Frog	<i>Microhyla berdmorei</i>	
5	Balloon Frog	<i>Uporodon globulus</i>	
6	Indian Bull Frog	<i>Hoplobatrachus tigerinus</i>	Dicroglossidae
7	Skipping Frog	<i>Euphlyctis cyanophlycits</i>	
8	Cricket Frog	<i>Fejervarya limnocharis</i>	
9	Cope's Frog	<i>Sylvirana leptoglossa</i>	Ranidae

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
10	Marsh Frog	<i>Hyla annectans</i>	Hylidae
11	Common Tree frog	<i>Polypsdates leucomystax</i>	Rhacophoridae

• Checklist of Mammal Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
1	Irrawaddy Squirrel	<i>Callosciurus pygerythrus</i>	Sciuridae
2	Jungle Cat	<i>Felis chaus</i>	Felidae
3	Bengal Fox	<i>Vulpes bengalensis</i>	Canidae
4	Asistic Jackal	<i>Canis aureus</i>	
5	Indian Flying Fox	<i>Pteropus giganteus</i>	Pteropodidae
6	False Vampire Bat	<i>Megaderma lyra</i>	Megadermatidae
7	Rhesus Macaque	<i>Macaca mulatta</i>	Cercopithecidae
8	Small Indian Mongoose	<i>Herpestes auropunctatus</i>	Herpestidae
9	Common Mongoose	<i>Herpestes edwardsii</i>	
10	Large Indian Civet	<i>Viverra zibetha</i>	Viverridae
11	Common Palm Civet	<i>Paradoxurus hermaphroditus</i>	
12	Small Indian Civet	<i>Viverricula indica</i>	verridae
13	Wild Boar	<i>Sus scrofa</i>	Suidae

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
14	Barking Dear	<i>Muntiacus muntjak</i>	Cervidae
15	Spotted Deer	<i>Axis axis</i>	
16	Brush-tailed Porcupine	<i>Atherurus macrourus</i>	Hystricidae
17	House Rat	<i>Rattus rattus</i>	Muridae
18	Long Tail Tree Mouse	<i>Vandeleuria oleracea</i>	

• Checklist of Reptile Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
1	Common River Terrapin	<i>Batagur baska</i>	Geoemydidae
2	Indian Roofed Turtle	<i>Pangshura tecta</i>	
3	Black Pond Turtle	<i>Geoclemys hamiltonii</i>	Hystricidae
4	Common Garden Lizard	<i>Calotes versicolor</i>	Muridae
5	Gecko	<i>Gekko gekko</i>	
6	Spotted House Lizard	<i>Hemidactylus frenatus</i>	Gekkonidae
7	Brook's House Gecko	<i>Hemidactylus brookii</i>	
8	Bengal Monitor	<i>Varanus bengalensis</i>	Varanidae
9	Yellow Monitor Lizard	<i>Varanus flavescens</i>	
10	Common Krait	<i>Bungarus caeruleus</i>	Elapidae
11	Spectacled Cobra	<i>Naja naja</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
12	Striped Keelback	<i>Amphiesma stolatum</i>	Colubridae
13	Checkered Keelback	<i>Xenochrophis piscator</i>	
14	Common Vine Snake	<i>Ahaetulla nasuta</i>	
15	Indian Rat Snake	<i>Ptyas mucosa</i>	
16	Painted bronzeback	<i>Dendrelaphis pictus</i>	
17	Banded kukri snake	<i>Oligodon arnensis</i>	
18	Gharial	<i>Gavialis gangeticus</i>	Gavialidae
19	Brahminy blind snake	<i>Indotyphlops braminus</i>	Typhlopidae

• Checklist of Butterfly Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
1	Chocolate Albatross	<i>Appias lyncida</i>	Pieridae
2	Common Emigrant	<i>Catopsilia pomona</i>	
3	Common Grass Yellow	<i>Eurema hecabe</i>	
4	Common Jezebel	<i>Delias eucharis</i>	
5	Common Wanderer	<i>Pareronia valeria</i>	
6	Mottled Emigrant	<i>Catopsilia pyranthe</i>	
7	Painted Jezebel	<i>Delias hyparete indica</i>	
8	Psyche	<i>Leptosia nina</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
9	Red-base Jezebel	<i>Delias pasithoei</i>	Pieridae
10	Red-spot Jezebel	<i>Delias descombesi</i>	
11	Striped Albatross	<i>Appias libythea olferna</i>	
12	Three Spotted Grass	<i>Eurema blanda sylhetana</i>	
13	Tree Yellow	<i>Gandaca harina</i>	
14	Angled Castor	<i>Ariadne ariadne pallidior</i>	Nymphalidae
15	Black Rajah	<i>Charaxes solon</i>	
16	Black vein sergeant	<i>Athyma ranga</i>	
17	Chestnut-Streaked Sailor	<i>Neptis jumbah</i>	
18	Chocolate Sailor	<i>Neptis harita</i>	
19	Chocolate Pansy	<i>Precis iphita</i>	
20	Clipper	<i>Parthenos sylvia</i>	
22	Color Sergeant	<i>Athyma inara</i>	
23	Commander	<i>Moduza procris</i>	
24	Common Baron	<i>Euthalia aconthea garuda</i>	
25	Common Castor	<i>Ariadne merione</i>	
26	Common Jester	<i>Pantoporia hordonia</i>	
27	Common Map	<i>Cyrestis thyodamas</i>	
28	Common Nawab	<i>Polyura athamus</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
29	Common Sailor	<i>Neptis hylas</i>	Nymphalidae
30	Common Sergeant	<i>Athyma opalina</i>	
31	Courtesan	<i>Euripus nyctelius</i>	
32	Danaied Eggfly	<i>Hypolimnas misippus</i>	
33	Great Eggfly	<i>Hypolimnas bolina</i>	
34	Grey Count	<i>Tanaecia lepidea</i>	
35	Grey Pansy	<i>Junonia atlites</i>	
36	Jewelled Nawab	<i>Polyura delphis</i>	
37	Knight	<i>Lebadea martha</i>	
38	Lemon Pansy	<i>Junonia lemonias</i>	
39	Leopard Lacewing	<i>Cethosia cyane</i>	
40	Orange Staff Sergeant	<i>Athyma cama</i>	
41	Peacock Pansy	<i>Junonia almana</i>	
42	Popinjay	<i>Stibochiona nicea nicea</i>	
43	Powdered Baron	<i>Euthalia monina</i>	
44	Staff Sergeant	<i>Athyma selenophora</i>	
45	Tawny Rajah	<i>Charaxes psaphon imna</i>	
46	Vagrant	<i>Vagrans egista sinha</i>	
47	White Bodered Blue Baron	<i>Euthalia phemius</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
48	White Edge Blue Baron	<i>Euthalia phemius</i>	Nymphalidae
49	Yellow Pansy	<i>Junonia hierta</i>	
50	Common Earl	<i>Tanaecia jului</i>	
51	Scarce White Commodore	<i>Limenitis zulema</i>	
52	Cruiser	<i>Vindula erota</i>	
53	Angled Pierrot	<i>Caleta decidia decidia</i>	Lycaenidae
54	Banded Blue Pierrot	<i>Discolampa ethion</i>	
55	Common Cerulean	<i>Jamides celeno</i>	
56	Dark Cerulean	<i>Jamides bochus</i>	
57	Common Imperial	<i>Cheritra freja evansi</i>	
58	Common Lineblue	<i>Prosotas nora ardates</i>	
59	Tailless Lineblue	<i>Prosotas dubiosa indica</i>	
60	Common Ciliate Blue	<i>Anthene emolus</i>	
61	Common Tinsel	<i>Catapaecilma major major</i>	
62	Common Pierrot	<i>Castalius rosimon rosimon</i>	
63	Common Tit	<i>Hypolycaena erylus</i>	
64	Dark Grass Blue	<i>Zizeeria karsandra</i>	
65	Pale Grass Blue	<i>Pseudozizeeria maha</i>	
67	Copper Flash	<i>Rapala pheretima</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
68	Common Hedgeblue	<i>Acytolepis puspa</i>	Lycaenidae
69	White-Disc Hedgeblue	<i>Celatoxia albidisca</i>	
70	Hooked Oakblue	<i>Arhopala paramuta</i>	
71	Indian Cupid	<i>Everes lacturnus assamica</i>	
72	Indian Sunbeam	<i>Curetis thetis</i>	
73	Lesser Grass Blue	<i>Zizzeria otis</i>	
74	Lime Blue	<i>Chilades laius laius</i>	
75	Little Cerulean Oakblue	<i>Arhopala ammonides</i>	
76	Sylhet Oakblue	<i>Arhopala silhetensis</i>	
77	Large Oakblue	<i>Arhopala amantes</i>	
78	Green Oakblue	<i>Arhopala eumolphus</i>	
79	Dusted Oakblue	<i>Arhopala bazaloides</i>	
80	Hooked Oakblue	<i>Arhopala paramuta</i>	
81	Orchid Tit	<i>Chliaria othoma othoma</i>	
82	Pea Blue	<i>Lampides boeticus</i>	
83	Quaker	<i>Neopithecops zalmora</i>	
84	Tailless Lineblue	<i>Prosotas dubiosa indica</i>	
85	Tiny Grass Blue	<i>Zizula hylax</i>	
86	Yamfly	<i>Loxura atymnus</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
87	Malayan	<i>Megisba malaya</i>	Lycaenidae
88	Zebra blue	<i>Leptotes plinius</i>	
89	Bamboo Treebrown	<i>Lethe europa</i>	Satyridae
90	Common Evening Brown	<i>Melanitis leda ismene</i>	
91	Dark Evening Brown	<i>Melanitis phedima bela</i>	
92	Common Fivering	<i>Ypthima baldus</i>	
93	Common Palmfly	<i>Ypthima huebneri</i>	
94	Common Threering	<i>Elymnias hypermnestra</i>	
95	Dark Banded Bushbrown	<i>Ypthima pandocus</i>	
96	Dingy Bushbrown	<i>Mycalesis mineus</i>	
97	Lepcha Bushbrown	<i>Mycalesis perseus</i>	
98	Lesser Three Ring	<i>Mycalesis lepcha</i>	
99	Lilacine Bushbrown	<i>Ypthima inica</i>	
100	Nigger	<i>Mycalesis francisca</i>	
101	Tailed Red Forester	<i>Lethe sinorix</i>	
102	White Bar Bushbrown	<i>Mycalesisanaxias</i>	
102	Blue Crow	<i>Euploea klugii</i>	Danaiidae
103	Blue-spotted Crow	<i>Euploea midamus rogenhoferi</i>	
104	Blue Tiger	<i>Tirumala limniace</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
105	Common Crow	<i>Euploea core</i>	Danaidae
106	Dark BlueTiger	<i>Tirumala septentrionis</i>	
107	Glassy Tiger	<i>Parantica aglea</i>	
108	Long Branded Blue Crow	<i>Euploes deione</i>	
109	Plain Tiger	<i>Danaus chrysippus</i>	
120	Striped Blue crow	<i>Euploea mulciber</i>	
121	Striped Tiger	<i>Danaus genutia</i>	
122	Blue Mormon	<i>Papilio polymnestor</i>	Papilionidae
123	Common Batwing	<i>Atrophaneura varuna astorion</i>	
124	Common Birdwing	<i>Troides helena cerberus</i>	
125	Golden Birdwing	<i>Troides aecus aecus</i>	
126	Common Batwing	<i>Atrophaneura varuna astorion</i>	
127	Common Bluebottle	<i>Graphium sarpedon sarpedon</i>	
128	Common Jay	<i>Graphium doson</i>	
129	Common Mime	<i>Chilasa clytia</i>	
130	Common Mormon	<i>Papilio polytes</i>	
131	Common Rose	<i>Pachliopta aristolochiae</i>	
132	Five-bar Swordtail	<i>Pathysa antiphates</i>	
133	Golden Birdwing	<i>Troides aecus aecus</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
134	Great Mormon	<i>Papilio memnon</i>	Papilionidae
135	Great Zebra	<i>Graphium xenocles xenocles</i>	
136	Lime Butterfly	<i>Papilio demolius Linn</i>	
137	Red Helen	<i>Papilio helenus helenus</i>	
138	Tailed Jay	<i>Graphium agamemnon</i>	
139	Yellow-crested Spangle	<i>Papilio elephenor</i>	
140	Yellow Helen	<i>Papilio chaon</i>	
141	Brown Awl	<i>Badamia exclamationis</i>	Hesperiidae
142	Chestnut Angle	<i>Odontoptilum angulata</i>	
143	Chestnut Bob	<i>Iambrix salsala</i>	
144	Common Awl	<i>Hasora badra badra</i>	
145	Common Dartlet	<i>Oriens gola pseudolus</i>	
146	Common Red Eye	<i>Matapa aria</i>	
147	Black-veined Red Eye	<i>Matapa sasivarma</i>	
148	Common Snow Flat	<i>Tagiades japetus</i>	
149	Common Wight	<i>Iton semamora semamora</i>	
150	Conjoined Swift	<i>Pelopidas conjuncta</i>	
151	Dark Palm Dart	<i>Telicota ancilla bambusae</i>	
152	Forest Hopper	<i>Astictopterus jama olivascens</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
153	Fulvous Pied Flat	<i>Pseudocoladenia dan fabia</i>	Hesperiidae
154	Grass Demon	<i>Udaspes folus</i>	
155	Indian Awl King	<i>Choaspes benjamini formosana</i>	
156	Narrow Banded Velvet Bob	<i>Koruthaialos rubecula cachara</i>	
157	Restricted Demon	<i>Notocrypta curvifascia</i>	
158	Smaller Dartlet	<i>Oriens goloides</i>	
159	Straight Swift	<i>Parnara guttata mangala</i>	
160	Tree Flitter	<i>Hyarotis adrastus praba</i>	
161	Water Snow Flat	<i>Tagiadus litigiosa litigiosa</i>	
162	Small Green Awlet	<i>Bibasis amara</i>	
163	Orange Awlet	<i>Bibasis jaina</i>	
164	Moore's Ace	<i>Halpe porus</i>	
165	Tufted Ace	<i>Sebastonyma dolopia</i>	
166	Suffused Snow Flat	<i>Tagiades gana athas</i>	
167	Common Snow Flat	<i>Togiades japetus ravi Moore</i>	
168	Common Grass Dart	<i>Taractrocera mevius maevius</i>	
169	Besta Palm Dart	<i>Telicata besta beste</i>	
170	Common Palm Dart	<i>Telicata colon stinga</i>	
171	Linna Palm Dart	<i>Telicota linna linna</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
172	Grass Demon	<i>Udaspes folus</i>	Hesperiidae
173	Hoary palmer	<i>Unkana ambasa</i>	
174	Detached Dart	<i>Potanthus trachala tytleri</i>	
175	Bevan's Swift	<i>Pseudohorbo bevani</i>	
176	Fulvous Pied Flat	<i>Pseudocoladenia dan fabia</i>	
177	Coon/Dusky Partwing	<i>Soncus fuligo subfasciatus</i>	
178	Common Small Flat	<i>Sarangesa dasahara dasahara</i>	
179	Forest Bob	<i>Scobura isoto Swinhoe</i>	
180	Ceylon Swift	<i>Parnara bada boda</i>	
181	Continental Swift	<i>Parnara ganga</i>	
182	Light Straw Ace	<i>Pithauria stramineipennis</i>	
183	Bengal Swift	<i>Pelopidas agna agna</i>	
184	Great Swift	<i>Pelopidas assamensis de</i>	
185	Contiguous Swift	<i>Polytremis lubricans</i>	
186	Small Branded Swift	<i>Pelopidas Mathias Mathias</i>	
187	Chinese Swift	<i>Pelopidas sinensia</i>	
188	Large Branded Swift	<i>Pelopidas subochracea</i>	
189	Confucian Dart	<i>Potanthus confucius dushto</i>	
190	Indian Dart	<i>Potanthus pseudomaesa clio</i>	

Sl no	English Name	Scientific Name	Family
191	Double-banded Judy	<i>Abisara bifosciata</i>	Riodinidae
192	<i>Plum Judy</i>	<i>Abisara echerius suffusa</i>	
193	<i>Harlequin</i>	<i>Taxila hoquinus fasciata</i>	
194	<i>Punchinello</i>	<i>Zemerus flegyas flegyas</i>	

• Checklist of Insect Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	Common Name	Scientific Name	Family	Order
1	Transverse ladybird beetle	<i>Coccinella transversalis</i>	Coccinellidae	Coleoptera
2	Epilachna ladybird beetle	<i>Epilachna vigintioctopunctata</i>		
3	Fungus beetle	<i>Ancylopus melanocephalus</i>	Endomychidae	
4	Golden-spotted tiger beetle	<i>Cicindela aurulenta</i>	Cicindelidae	
5	Tiger beetle	<i>C. octonotata</i>		
6	Blister beetle	<i>Mylabris cichorri</i>		
7	Gold-dust Beetle	<i>Hypomeces squamosus</i>		
8	Dung beetle	<i>Anthophila aegyptiaca</i>		
9	Praying mantis	<i>Mantis religiosa</i>	Meloidae	Dictyoptera

Sl no	Common Name	Scientific Name	Family	Order
10	Asian tiger mosquito	<i>Aedes albopictus</i>	Curculionidae	Diptera
11	Jungle mosquito	<i>Armigeres flavus</i>	Scarabaeidae	
12	Predator mosquito	<i>Toxorhynchites bengalensis</i>		
13	Horse fly	<i>Tabanus rubidus</i>	Tabanidae	
14	Housefly	<i>Musca domestica</i>	Muscidae	
15	Green Bottle fly	<i>Lucilla sericata</i>	Calliphoridae	
16	Green stink bug	<i>Nezara viridula</i>	Pentatomidae	Hemiptera
17	Radish bug	<i>Eurydema pulchrum</i>		
18	Assassin bug	<i>Polytoxus fuscovittus</i>		
19	Asian assassin bug	<i>Euagoras plagiatus</i>	Reduviidae	
20	Assassin bug	<i>Rhinocoris segmentarius</i>		
21	Green cicadas	<i>Dundubia ensifera</i>	Cicadidae	Homoptera
22	Aphid	<i>Aphis gossypii</i>	Aphididae	
23	Live wood termite	<i>Odontotermes parvidens</i>	Termitidae	Isoptera
24	Live wood termite	<i>Microtermes obesi</i>		
25	Alder fly	<i>Neochauliodes simplex</i>	Corydalidae	Neuroptera
26	Green lace wing	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	Chrysopidae	

Sl no	Common Name	Scientific Name	Family	Order
27	Asiatic honey bee	<i>Apis cerana</i>	Apidae	Hymenoptera
28	Giant honey bee	<i>A. dorsata</i>		
29	Carpenter bee	<i>Xylocopa aestuans</i>		
30	Tropical carpenter bee	<i>X. latipes</i>		
31	Bumble bee	<i>X. rufa</i>		
32	Megachile leaf-cutter	<i>Megachile disjuncta</i>		
33	Velvet sugar ant	<i>Camponotus rufoglaucus</i>	Megachilidae	
34	Carpenter ant	<i>C. festinus</i>	Formicidae	
35	The Saint Valentine ant	<i>Cremastogaster abdominalis</i>		
36	Red wood ant	<i>Cr. rufa</i>		
37	Red fire ant	<i>Myrmica indica</i>		
38	Destructive trailing ant	<i>Trichomyrmex criniceps</i>		
39	Toothed ant	<i>Odontoponera denticulata</i>		
40	Black slender ant	<i>Tetraoponera nigra</i>		
41	Tropical fire ant	<i>Solenopsis geminata</i>		
42	Big headed ant	<i>Pheidole binghamii</i>		
43	The greater banded hornet	<i>Vespa tropica</i>		Vespidae

Sl no	Common Name	Scientific Name	Family	Order
44	The yellow paper wasp	<i>Polistes olivaceus</i>	Vespidae	Hymenoptera
45	Mango defoliator	<i>Cricula trifenestra</i>	Saturniidae	Lepidoptera
46	Atlas moth	<i>Attacus atlas</i>		
47	Albizia defoliator	<i>Rhesala imparata</i>	Noctuidae	
48	Cadamba defoliators	<i>Antitrygodes cuneilinea</i>	Geometridae	
49	Teak skeletonizer	<i>Eutectona machaeralis</i>	Crambidae	
50	Slender skimmer	<i>Orthetrum sabina</i>	Libellulidae	Odonata
51	Skimmer	<i>Or. testaceum</i>		
52	Skimmer	<i>Urothemis signata</i>		
53	Common Clubtail	<i>Actinogomphus rapax</i>	Gomphidae	
54	Golden Dartlet	<i>Ischnura aurora</i>	Coenagriidae	
55	Short horned grasshopper	<i>Choroedocus robustus</i>	Acrididae	Orthoptera
56	Short horned grasshopper	<i>Oxya japonica</i>		
57	Cricket	<i>Gryllus confirmatus</i>	Gryllidae	
58	Field cricket	<i>Brachytrypes orientalis</i>		
59	Asian mole cricket	<i>Gryllotalpa orientalis</i>	Gryllotalpidae	
60	Crickets	<i>Euscyrtus concinnus</i>		
61	Meadow Grasshopper	<i>Conocephalus longipennis</i>	Tettigoniidae	

• Checklist of fish Species of Bhawal National Park

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
1	Rui	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	Cyprinidae
2	Catla	<i>Catla catla</i>	
3	Mrigal	<i>Cirrhinus cirrhosus</i>	
4	Kalibaush	<i>Labeo calbasu</i>	
5	Gonia	<i>Labeo gonius</i>	
6	Grasscarp	<i>Ctenopharyn godonidella</i>	
7	Bata	<i>Labeo bata</i>	
8	Lachu	<i>Cirrhinus reba</i>	
9	Mola	<i>Amblypharyn godonmola</i>	
10	Dhela	<i>Osteo bramacotio</i>	
11	Chela	<i>Salmostoma phulo</i>	
12	Darkina	<i>Esomous danricus</i>	
13	Tit punt	<i>Puntius ticto</i>	
14	JatPunti	<i>P. sophore</i>	
15	Teri punti	<i>Puntius terio</i>	
16	Jhilipunti	<i>Pethia gelius</i>	
17	Sharpunti	<i>Puntius sarana</i>	
18	Raj punti	<i>Puntius gonoinotus</i>	
19	Silvercarp	<i>Hypophthalmicthys molitrix</i>	

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
20	Banshpata	<i>Devario devario</i>	Cyprinidae
21	Gutum	<i>Lepidocephalus guntea</i>	Cobitidae
22	Kakila	<i>Xenentodon cancila</i>	Belontiidae
23	Ek thota	<i>Dermogenys pusilla</i>	Hemiramphidae
24	Taki	<i>Channa punctatus</i>	Channidae
25	Cheng	<i>Channa orientalis</i>	
26	Shol	<i>Channa striatus</i>	
27	Gozar	<i>Channa marulius</i>	
28	Chapila	<i>Gudusia chapra</i>	Clupeidae
29	Katchki	<i>Corica soborna</i>	
30	Kanpona	<i>Aplocheilus panchax</i>	Aplocheilidae
31	Foli	<i>Notopterus notopterus</i>	Notopteriidae
32	Lamba chanda	<i>Chanda nama</i>	Ambassidae
33	Lal chanda	<i>Parambassis lala</i>	
34	Gol chanda	<i>Parambassis ranga</i>	
35	Koi	<i>Anabas testudineus</i>	Anabantidae
36	Tilapia	<i>Oreochromis mossambicus</i>	Cichlidae
37	Bele	<i>Glossogobius giuris</i>	Gobiidae
38	Meni	<i>Nandus nandus</i>	Nandidae

Sl no	Local Name	Scientific Name	Family
39	Boro khalisha	<i>Colisa fasciatus</i>	Osphronemidae
40	Choto khalisha	<i>Colisa chuno</i>	
41	Lal khalisha	<i>Colisa lalia</i>	
42	Gulsha	<i>Mystus cavasius</i>	Bagridae
43	Bujuri	<i>Mystus tengra</i>	
44	Tengra	<i>Mystus vittatus</i>	
45	Shing	<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i>	Heteropneustidae
46	Magur	<i>Clarius batrachus</i>	Clariidae
47	Batasi	<i>Pseudeutropius atherinoides</i>	Schilbeidae
48	Boal	<i>Wallago attu</i>	Siluridae
49	Pabda	<i>Ompok pabo</i>	
50	Kani pabda	<i>Ompok bimaculatus</i>	
51	Madhu pabda	<i>Ompok pabda</i>	
52	Boro Baim	<i>Mastacembelus armatus</i>	Mastacembelidae
53	Guchi	<i>Macrogathus pancalus</i>	
54	Tara Baim	<i>Macrogathus aculeatus</i>	
55	Kuchia	<i>Monopterusuchia</i>	Synbranchidae
56	Potka	<i>Tetraodon cutcutia</i>	Tetraodontidae
57	Kalo icha	<i>Macrobrachium malcolmsonii</i>	Palaemonidae
58	Sada icha	<i>Macrobrachium sp.</i>	

Conclusion

Bhawal National Park, a vital ecological sanctuary in Bangladesh, showcases a rich tapestry of biodiversity and natural ecosystems. The park spans over 5,022 hectares and is home to a diverse range of flora and fauna. The flora includes 369 plant species, with 127 tree species, 111 shrubs, 106 herbs, and 25 climbers¹. The unique coppice sal forest is a notable feature, providing a habitat for various wildlife species.

Despite its ecological significance, Bhawal National Park faces challenges due to anthropogenic activities. Illegal deforestation and land-use changes have led to a significant decline in forest cover, with nearly 49% of the forest depleted between 2005 and 2020. This has impacted the park's biodiversity, with many species becoming rare or extinct.

Efforts to restore and conserve the park's biodiversity include reforestation and the introduction of species such as peacocks, deer, and pythons. Continued conservation initiatives are crucial to preserving this natural heritage. The park's rich biodiversity and unique ecosystems underscore the importance of sustainable management practices to ensure its protection for future generations.

References

- Islam, M. A., & Sato, N. (2012). "Human-forest interaction and its impact on forest conservation in Bangladesh: A case study in the Bhawal National Park." *Journal of Forestry Research*, 23(2), 229-236.
- Rahman, M. M., & Hassan, M. M. (2014). "Ecological diversity and conservation challenges of Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Bangladesh Journal of Forest Science*, 33(1), 45-56.
- Khan, S. A., & Islam, S. M. (2016). "Biodiversity assessment of Bhawal National Park: Current status and conservation strategies." *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation*, 8(4), 89-98.
- Chowdhury, R. M., & Hossain, M. A. (2010). "Flora and fauna diversity in Bhawal National Park: An overview." *Asian Journal of Conservation Biology*, 2(2), 76-84.
- Ahmad, M. S., & Rahman, M. A. (2011). "Visitor impact on forest ecosystem and management strategies in Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(5), 1236-1242.
- Ahmed, Z. U., & Rahman, M. A. (2009). "Floral diversity of Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Journal of Forestry Research*, 20(2), 157-164.
- Hossain, M. K., & Nahar, L. (2012). "Inventory of plant species in Bhawal National Park." *Bangladesh Journal of Botany*, 41(2), 191-199.
- Chowdhury, M. S. H., Koike, M., & Muhammed, N. (2009). "Emphasis on the socio-economic aspects of flora biodiversity in Bhawal National Park." *International Journal of Biodiversity and Conservation*, 1(7), 213-222.
- Rahman, M. A., & Hassan, M. M. (2013). "Ecological analysis of the plant communities in Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Taxonomy*, 20(1), 35-44.
- Alam, M. K., & Mohiuddin, M. (2007). "Medicinal plant diversity in Bhawal National Park and their conservation status." *Indian Journal of Traditional Knowledge*, 6(3), 510-513.
- Sarker, S. U., & Sarker, N. J. (1988). "Avifauna of Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Journal of Bombay Natural History Society*, 85(3), 599-605.
- Chowdhury, M. S. H., & Hossain, M. K. (2011). "Birds of Bhawal National Park: Diversity and conservation." *Journal of Threatened Taxa*, 3(8), 2023-2034.
- Khan, M. M. H., & Sultana, P. (2009). "Status and habitat preferences of birds in Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Ecological Research*, 24(4), 807-815.
- Islam, M. A., & Hasan, M. A. (2003). "A checklist of the birds of Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Bangladesh Journal of Zoology*, 31(1),

- Chowdhury, M. A. K., & Bashar, M. A. (2022). Diversity and abundance of some insect fauna in Bhawal and Madhupur Sal forests of Bangladesh. *Journal of Biodiversity Conservation and Bioresource Management*, 7(1), 11-24.
- Hossain, M. A., & Islam, M. N. (2010). "Mammalian diversity and their conservation in Bhawal National Park, Bangladesh." *Journal of Threatened Taxa*, 2(3), 761-769.
- Khan, M. M. H., & Sultana, P. (2011). "Amphibians and reptiles of Bhawal National Park: Diversity and conservation status." *Herpetological Review*, 42(4), 575-582.
- Rahman, M. M., & Chowdhury, S. U. (2013). "Insect diversity and ecological roles in Bhawal National Park." *Journal of Entomology and Nematology*, 5(2), 20-28.
- Islam, M. S., & Hasan, M. A. (2012). "An overview of the fish species in the aquatic ecosystems of Bhawal National Park." *Bangladesh Journal of Fisheries Research*, 14(2), 43-53.